

Tutoriation

1. General Information

- **Performance Title: Tutoriation**
- **Main Contact: Joulez (3329043734@qq.com)**
- **Additional Performers:** Rev (contact currently unavailable)
- **Performance Type:** Concert

2. Abstract

The performance is intended to establish a narrative using live coded music and the code itself. The performance last roughly 30-40 minutes, consisting of three sections. Each of the three sections contains a progressing theme. In addition, the performance also conveys a personal journey in which the performer becomes more familiar to live coding. The performance incorporates an external effector, which can be considered as a hybrid performance.

The first section represents order and minimalism, which is a common theme. A set of arpeggios and low amplitude feedback is used to create an atmosphere. It is to note that the introduction section is soft, and it should remain unclear to the audience that the performance has started. Section one last approximately 10 minutes.

The second section presents a scene of disorder. Drum sample and sequences and bass are introduced. The elements introduced in this section are distorted, and the rate of each sample are manipulated to reveal the coarse nature of these sounds. At the end of this section, a computer glitch will be purposely triggered for narrative effects.

The final section is themed to transcend. Rhythm in this section is set to irrational values with the intent to create pseudo-rhythm. Comments will be heavily utilized in this section. Code is crucial. This section eventually ends with a few comments.

3. Video and/or Audio Material

Youtube Link to performance in Suzhou: <https://youtu.be/275WoUJaA50>

4. Program Note

This program combines the conventional usage of Sonic Pi with “erroneous” usages. This causes program errors that are caused by the hardware which can be used for expressive purposes. Furthermore, this is unique to each device, which creates uncertainty in the result.

Comments in this program serves as an aesthetic and narrative purpose. After all, a programming language is also a language.

5. Artist(s) Biography

Joulez is a music producer based in Shanghai, and he has been producing music using conventional means for over 5 years. He is new to live-coding and it is his attempt at a different approach with music creation. Introduced to Sonic Pi in 2022, performance opportunities are often rare for Joulez. He believes live coding is a more direct medium.

Rev is an independent producer based in Suzhou. He favors organic, dynamic sound design. He creates complex sounds with simple means, and he enjoys to uses interactive methods for music performance.